

AN ANALYSIS OF THE LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE ABOUT ONLINE TRADING MECHANISM AMONG INVESTORS

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ABSTRACT

The current research is meant to gauge investors' familiarity with the stock market, its workings, and the SEBI's regulations. Researchers want to gauge participants' familiarity with stock exchanges and the Securities and Exchange Board of India. Statisticians used the standard deviation, mean, frequency, and percentage analysis to make sense of the data. According to the research, investors know very little about SEBI's regulations, client training, and community outreach. Therefore, SEBI must travel both to the rural and urban areas to educate people about the stock market, online trading, systematic investment plans, and a grievance cell.

Keywords: *Standard Deviation, Securities and Exchange Board of India, Client Training, Equity Markets*

INTRODUCTION

Investing in knowledge yields the highest rate of return; it is the only path to ultimate independence. The best way to raise investor awareness and safeguard their interests is through education. This means that having a solid grasp of the fundamentals of personal finance is essential for achieving success as an investor. When investors lose faith in the stock market, it casts doubt on the reliability of the available data and has a knock-on effect on their market participation. This is especially true given the stock market's notoriously opaque nature and its penchant for manipulative pricing strategies. When it comes to investing in the stock market, Indian investors are good at saving money but lack experience due to a lack of understanding of financial products, programmes, and markets. Even though the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) is a regulatory body whose primary function is to safeguard investors' funds, the public remains wary of the stock market. SEBI needs to host investor awareness workshops to dispel this fear by teaching people about the stock market.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Researchers Dr. K. Banumathy and Dr. R. Azhagaiah (2016) looked at people's knowledge of stock market investments and found that it varied widely depending on demographic factors like gender, age, education level, and profession. They also discovered that there was a noticeable gap between

investors of different ages and professions. Mayank (2009) conducted an analysis of the impact of external funding on Indian corporate governance norms by looking at the roles of the regulator and the capital market.

The article reviews the role of external finance and examines the altering pattern of India's reliance on it as the country's economy evolves. According to research by Kathuria and Singhania (2010), newspapers and financial websites are the two most influential information channels for investors. Investors favoured safe investments including postal savings, insurance, and public provident funds.

Investors, according to Kumar Rajesh and Arora R. S. (2013), should increase their level of awareness through watching television, reading newspapers and magazines, and subscribing to specialised publications that cover the investing industry. According to Puneet Bhushan(2013), most respondents have a middling understanding of personal finance.

While he agrees that a person's financial literacy is strongly influenced by demographic characteristics like gender, income, education level, and industry or workplace, he disagrees with the widely held belief that a person's location has much of an impact on his or her financial acumen. Modern urban India's employed youth have a degree of financial knowledge that is on par with that of their peers in other developed countries.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The objective of the study is to assess the Level of Knowledge about Online Trading Mechanism among Investors.

METHODOLOGY

The study is analytical. The data represents for the study is collected through a structured questionnaire with a sample of 200 NSE investors who are investing in the IT sector. The convenience random sampling technique was used to select the sample for the study. Secondary data was collected through online journals, SEBI website, newspapers. MS-Excel was used to calculate the primary data by using statistical tools like frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation.

DATA ANALYSIS

Table 1 Demographic Profile of the Investors

Particulars		No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	120	60
	Female	80	40
	Total	200	100
Age	25 years	8	4
	26-40 years	60	30
	41-50 years	96	48
	51 years and above	36	18
	Total	200	100
Monthly Income	Rs.10,000	4	2
	Rs.10,001- Rs.25,000	10	5
	Rs.25,001-Rs.50,000	94	47
	Rs.50,001 & above	92	46

	Total	200	100
Education Profile	School	10	5
	Graduate	30	15
	Post-Graduation	140	70
	Others	20	10
	Total	200	100
Occupational Profile	Private	172	87
	Public	4	2
	Self-Employed	2	1
	Government	10	5
	Others specify	10	5
	Total	200	100

(Source: Calculated from Primary Data)

As can be seen in the table above, 60% of the male respondents are stock market investors, whereas only 40% of the female respondents are stock market investors. Comparatively, when broken down by age bracket, we see that 48% of investors fall somewhere between the ages of 41 and 50, 30% fall between the ages of 26 and 40, 18% fall between the ages of 51 and above, and the remaining 4% fall somewhere between the ages of 25 and 34. Of the respondents, 47% have monthly income between Rs.25,001 and Rs.50,000 and 46% earn between Rs.50,001 and Rs.100,000, while 5% and 2%, respectively, have monthly income between Rs.10,001 and Rs.25,000 and Rs.10,000. Seventy percent of stock market investors have advanced degrees and fifteen percent have bachelor's degrees, while ten percent and five percent, respectively, have diplomas, certifications, and high school diplomas. Eighty-seven percent of respondents work for private companies, two percent work for public companies, five percent work for the government, five percent work in agriculture, sports, or other fields, and one percent are self-employed.

Table 2 Investors awareness of stock market

	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	200	100
No	0	0
Total	200	100

(Source: Calculated from Primary data)

It is clear from the data above that investors have a solid grasp of the workings of the stock market, as all respondents reported having some familiarity with the financial industry.

Table 3 Frequency of investment in the stock market

	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Regularly	156	78
Occasionally	44	22
Not At All	0	0
Total	200	100

(Source: Calculated from Primary data)

Investors who participate in the capital market on a regular basis are shown in the table above to have a greater understanding of the stock market and the various investment opportunities it presents compared to those who only invest on rare occasions. Therefore, SEBI needs to run awareness campaigns on the stock market schemes such equity funds, debt funds, and so on to encourage investors to engage more heavily in the capital market.

Table 4 Yearly investment in securities

	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Less Than 50000	104	52
50000-100000	20	10
100000-500000	42	21
500000 And Above	34	17
Total	200	100

(Source: Calculated from Primary data)

According to the aforementioned table, investors who invest between \$50,000 and \$100,000 consistently make money. So, in order to save money, they can invest in Systematic Investment Plans (SIP), whereas investors with a yearly investment of \$1.0 million to \$5.0 million and \$5.0 million and above can choose to invest in securities in a lump sum, which will allow them to benefit from future market growth and increase their returns.

Table 5 Reliable sources of information on investment in securities

	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Company Financial	58	29
Investor Forum	60	30
TV Channels	10	5
Stock Market Announcement	20	10
Technical Analysis	20	10
Professional Consultant	32	16
Total	200	100

(Source: Calculated from Primary data)

The above table shows that investors look to the Investor forum and company financials as their primary sources of information before making any investment decisions. This is because these are the most trustworthy places for investors to learn about a company's financial standing, profit, and asset valuation. Investors who seek advice from professionals should have a firm grasp on the types of securities they wish to purchase and the level of risk they are willing to assume; those who rely on technical analysis should do extensive research into the company's share price before investing; and those who rely on stock market announcements should be wary of manipulative information about the company's share price.

Table 6 Investors Education Programme help to protect the investors

	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	86	43
Agree	46	23
Neutral	26	13
Disagree	26	13
Strongly Disagree	16	8
Total	200	100

(Source: Calculated from Primary data)

According to the data presented above, while 43% and 23% of investors believe that SEBI's Investor Education programmes are very helpful in safeguarding their savings, understanding financial products, and managing risk, respectively, 13%, 8%, and 13% of investors believe that they need to educate themselves on investor rights and duties in the stock market in order to confidently face the capital system.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Investors who work for private corporations may be considering increasing their stock market investments as a hedge against the possibility of losing their jobs. Employees of government agencies and publicly traded enterprises have ties to the government that allow them to invest occasionally in the stock market. Investors who are self-employed should put their money into the stock market if doing so will help them reach their financial objectives while also addressing their concerns about liquidity and risk. Low-risk, long-term investments allow investors to put away larger sums of money without sacrificing returns. Short-term and speculative investments offer high-risk, high-reward opportunities for investors. Stable growth securities are a good option for investors who can stomach some uncertainty in exchange for a steady return.

CONCLUSION

Innovations in technology, like as online trading, are hastening the already lightning-fast pace and heightened volatility of the financial markets around the world. Investors need a solid understanding of finance and the stock market in order to make sound decisions. Social media, investor meetings in smaller cities, a school-wide curriculum, and partnerships with brokers are all ways that SEBI may raise investor awareness and get the word out.

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